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Factors influencing consumers' food waste reduction behaviour at university canteens

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ABSTRACT

Understanding consumers' food waste behaviour has become increasingly crucial, given its adverse impacts on sustainability. Therefore, this study segmented consumers based on their food choice motives and investigated key factors influencing food waste reduction behaviour in university canteens employing attitude, social influence, and self-efficacy (ASE) framework extended with environmental concern, situational, and sociodemographic and lifestyle factors. An online survey was conducted in Denmark among university canteen users ($n = 438$). Hierarchical cluster analysis identified four segments, (1) Familiarity sensitive consumers – 34.9 % of participants, (2) Unconcerned consumers – 19.9 %, (3) Food for health and mood consumers – 19.2 %, and (4) Unfamiliar consumers – 26 %. Partial least squares structural equation modelling analysis shows that attitude, self-efficacy, and environmental concern significantly influenced behavioural intention, eventually influencing food waste reduction behaviour. Social influence and situational factors did not influence behavioural intention. Sensory appeal, price, health–mood, and familiarity significantly influenced behavioural attitude, whereas familiarity and weight control significantly influenced behaviour. Sociodemographic and lifestyle factors indirectly influence behavioural intention by their effects on attitudes, self-efficacy, and environmental concerns. Education, income, dietary patterns, and body mass index directly impacted food waste reduction behaviour. We suggest that improving consumers' attitudes and environmental concern while enhancing their self-efficacy might positively influence food waste reduction behaviour. Besides psychosocial factors, intervention should also consider focusing on consumers' food choice motives and sociodemographic and lifestyle factors to effectively influence food waste reduction behaviour in university canteen or similar settings.

1. Introduction

Globally, 931 million metric tonnes of food are wasted or lost annually, accounting for 17% of the total food produced (Forbes et al., 2021). According to the Food and Agricultural Organization (FAO) definitions, food waste is “the decrease in the quantity or quality of food resulting from decisions and actions by retailers, food service providers, and consumers.” In contrast, food loss refers to “the decrease in the quantity or quality of food resulting from decisions and actions by food suppliers in the chain, excluding retail, food service providers and consumers” (FAO, 2019). The FAO report shows that the amount of food waste in industrialised countries is similar to that of developing countries; however, the food loss in developing countries is during harvest and processing, whereas it

occurs during retail and consumer level in industrialised countries (Gustavsson, 2011). Food loss and waste are growing concerns due to their adverse environmental, economic, and social sustainability impacts. Previous studies have indicated that food waste and loss have high carbon, water, and ecological footprint (Gustafsson et al., 2013; Kummu et al., 2012; Santeramo, 2021) as well as responsible for a direct economic cost of about \$1 trillion (FAO, 2014). Further, reducing food waste and loss is essential for global food and nutrition security (Mokrane et al., 2023).

In the European Union, 88 million tonnes of food are wasted annually, with 41 million tonnes of food waste from households and 11 million tonnes from food services (Stenmarck et al., 2016). The United Nations Environment Programme, Food Index data, shows that most

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food waste is generated in Northern and Western Europe, where Denmark ranks third (Forbes et al., 2021). A report by Borum and Kidmose (2020) shows 103,000 metric tonnes of food waste generated in 2018 in Denmark, of which 13,300 were from catering and canteens. The study analysed avoidable and unavoidable food waste from 420 kg of mixed food waste generated from hotels, institutions, catering, and canteens which showed 62% of food waste was avoidable (Borum and Kidmose, 2020). In the food service sector, 51 % of fruits and vegetables, 15 % of meat, and 15 % of bakery product food waste generated were avoidable (Tonini et al., 2017).

The data from FAOSTAT shows that 40 % of the total food waste is generated at the consumption level (Priefer et al., 2016), and the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals targets to reduce global food waste at the consumer level by 50 % per capita by 2030 (FAO, 2019). Thus, several researchers have argued that understanding consumers' food waste behaviour is crucial for reducing food waste at the consumer level (Aktas et al., 2018; dos Santos et al., 2022; Stancu et al., 2016; Toti et al., 2019). Furthermore, previous studies have identified young consumers are one of the most significant segments responsible for generating food waste, mainly due to poor meal planning (Bravi et al., 2019; Ozanne et al., 2022). For example, in Denmark, young consumers aged 18 – 34 generate the most food waste, averaging 23 kg per person yearly (Stancu and Lhteenmki, 2018).

It is ideal for studying the food waste behaviour at the university canteen as it helps to reach a more significant number of the young population, meanwhile collecting accurate data about the amount, type of food wasted, and determinants of food waste behaviour (Li et al., 2021; Wyse et al., 2019). Further, it can provide valuable insights into young consumers' food consumption habits and preferences (Aires et al., 2021; García-Herrero et al., 2021). Tam et al. (2017) argue that young consumers spend a substantial amount of time at the university, while canteens play a crucial role in shaping their food consumption habits and preferences. Furthermore, young consumers' food consumption habits are highly influenced by integrating a set of attributes (food choice motives) based on their importance or salience for them at the point of choice (Boek et al., 2012; Hebden et al., 2015; Rangel, 2013). Understanding these food choice motives influencing food consumption habits is essential, as habit play is integral in explaining food waste behaviour (Russell et al., 2017). Moreover, researchers argue that in-depth studies focusing on exploring young consumers' food waste behaviours are needed to identify the key factors determining food waste reduction behaviour and develop effective strategies to reduce food waste (Aschemann-Witzel et al., 2015).

Several previous consumer studies have examined consumers' food waste behaviour. A quick search in the Scopus database with the following search string: (ALL ("food waste" OR "food loss") AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (behav* OR attitude* OR intention* OR belief* OR habit* OR practice* OR perception*)) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (consumer* OR participant* OR respondent*)) resulted in 3661 documents. Altogether, 200 studies were conducted in a university canteen setting, of which 34 focused on food waste. In contrast, the remaining studies focused on a broader concept, such as sustainable food consumption or were irrelevant. Among 34 studies, 16 employed exploratory survey design to understand food waste behaviour. These studies indicated that several factors influence food waste behaviour, including psychosocial and demographic factors such as attitudes (Iwasaki et al., 2021; Lazell, 2016; Lorenz et al., 2017; Pandey et al., 2023; Tarczyńska, 2021; Tsai et al., 2020; Zhang & Kwon, 2022), social influences (Lorenz et al., 2017; Mganga et al., 2021; Pandey et al., 2023; Tsai et al., 2020), habit (Morata et al., 2020), perceived behavioural control (Mganga et al., 2021; Tsai et al., 2020), and knowledge (Gabriel et al., 2021; Knezevic et al., 2019; Pandey et al., 2023; Yagoub et al., 2022). However, only one study was conducted in Denmark to understand surplus meal-buying behaviour (Pandey et al., 2023). Still, it was limited in explaining factors influencing food waste-reducing behaviour in a boarder context. Further, none of the studies segmented consumers based on

their food values and their role in attitudes and behaviour towards reducing food waste.

Several multidimensional health and non-health-related factors influence general food choices (De Boer et al., 2007; Ponis et al., 2017; Steptoe et al., 1995). These factors include health, mood, sensory appeal, natural content, convenience, price, weight control, familiarity, and ethical concerns (Steptoe et al., 1995). De Boer et al. (2007) put forward that these motives would guide consumers in shaping their attitudes and behaviour towards sustainable food choices. Previous studies have found that consumers' food choice motives play an influential role in food waste prevention behaviour in out-of-home eating settings (Aschemann-Witzel et al., 2015; Teng et al., 2022).

Taken together, this paper aims to segment consumers based on their food choice motives and understand the factors influencing consumers' food waste behaviour in university canteens by applying attitude, social influence, self-efficacy (ASE) framework with environmental concern, situational, sociodemographic and lifestyle factors as extended constructs. Further, this study will explore whether food choice motives influence consumers' attitudes and behaviour towards reducing food waste.

2. Theoretical framework and research hypothesis development

2.1. Attitude-social influence-efficacy (ASE) framework

The ASE framework is an extension of the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) (Ajzen & Fishbein, 1980) that consists of attitude and the subjective norm or social influence from TRA with the addition of self-efficacy from the Social Learning Theory (Bandura, 1977). According to the ASE framework, attitude (positive or negative evaluation of behavioural consequences), social influence (social support and pressure), and self-efficacy (assessment of abilities and possibilities) are the proximal cognitive factors that determine an individual's intention and behaviour (De Vries & Mudde, 1998). It is a widely used social cognition model that predicts and explains the intention to perform a particular behaviour (de Vries et al., 1988). The framework has been widely applied to predict health and dietary-related behaviour, mainly predicting intention to consume healthy eating behaviour (Brug et al., 1995; Pandey et al., 2021; Sandvik et al., 2007; Sheeran et al., 2016). Ajzen and Fishbein's attitude (Coşkun & Yetkin Özbük, 2020; Russell et al., 2017; Stancu et al., 2016) and social influence (Aktas et al., 2018; Graham-Rowe et al., 2015; Stancu et al., 2016) as well as Bandura's self-efficacy (Aschemann-Witzel et al., 2020; Jang & Lee, 2022; Kim et al., 2022) are widely used factors for predicting food waste behaviour among consumers. Therefore, the study hypothesises that H1–H3 = *attitude, social influence, and self-efficacy positively influence the intention to reduce food waste behaviour*, and H4 = *intention has a significant positive impact on reducing food waste behaviour*.

2.2. Incorporating new constructs in the ASE

The social cognition models are limited when trying to understand complex behaviours such as food waste behaviour; thus, previous research has applied additional constructs to increase the predictive capability of the framework (Armitage & Conner, 2000; Yuriev et al., 2020). Including some domain-specific constructs has improved the predictive power of such a framework (Abraham et al., 2011; Ogdén, 2003; Pandey et al., 2021). The present study has also attempted to include new constructs (situational factors, environmental concern, food choice motives, and sociodemographic and lifestyle factors) in the ASE based on the extant literature.

2.2.1. Situational factors

Previous research has added situational factors as an additional construct to predict food waste behaviour among consumers (Bell & Ulhas, 2020; Karim Ghani et al., 2013; Szakos et al., 2021; Wong, 2019).

For example, food waste behaviour is directly affected by situational factors such as smell, appearance, appetite towards the food, level of hunger, and the taste of food (Miroso et al., 2016; Schneider, 2008). Moreover, time constraints are a situational factor determining the amount of food waste consumers generate (Laven, 2017; Lorenz et al., 2017). Thus, the hypothesis H5 = *situational factor significantly influences intention to reduce food waste behaviour*.

2.2.2. Environmental concern

Food waste is one of the significant contributors to climate change (FAO, 2019). A study conducted among Romanian consumers showed a lack of awareness of environmental consequences related to food waste. Previous studies have shown awareness of climate change to be a significant predictor of intention to reduce food waste behaviour (Bell & Ulhas, 2020; Kim & Hall, 2019). Thus, H6 = *Perceived environmental concern positively influences the intention to reduce food waste behaviour*.

2.2.3. Food choice motives

Food choice motives and eating preferences are related to moral and health aspects of eating – affecting the food purchasing decisions that follow (Aktas et al., 2018; De Boer et al., 2007; Ponis et al., 2017). Previous studies have indicated that sensory appeal (de Hooge et al., 2017; Symmank et al., 2018; Teng et al., 2022; Appleton et al., 2019), price sensitivity (Abdelradi, 2018; Teng et al., 2022; Neff et al., 2015; Quested et al., 2013; Williams et al., 2012), health and safety (Principato et al., 2015; Teng et al., 2022; Visschers et al., 2016) play a crucial role in preventing food waste. For example, Swedish consumers who had a positive attitude towards the importance of price resulted in less household food waste when compared to the ones who reported less importance of price (Williams et al., 2012). Further, a previous study highlights that familiarity can develop the acceptance of green bins, influencing consumers' attitudes towards reducing food waste (Ladele et al., 2021). Therefore, H7 = *food choice motives factors positively influence attitude to reduce food waste*.

H8 = *food choice motive factors positively influence reducing food waste behaviour*.

2.2.4. Sociodemographic and lifestyle factors

Sociodemographic and lifestyle factors are linked with food waste behaviour (Gabriel et al., 2021; Knezevic et al., 2019; Morone et al., 2018; Pandey et al., 2023; Wiśniewska & Czernyszewicz, 2023; Yagoub et al., 2022; Zhang et al., 2021). For example, previous studies have shown that higher income (Stefan et al., 2013) and household size (Koivupuro et al., 2012) are associated with more food waste. Further, the influence of age on food waste behaviour was mixed, as previous studies show contrasting findings (Quested et al., 2013; Stefan et al., 2013). A study conducted in Denmark showed that age, gender, employment status, and household size were modest predictors of food waste behaviour (Grasso et al., 2019). Lastly, a higher level of education was associated with a higher awareness of food waste (Fox et al., 2018). Thus H9–H14 = *Sociodemographic and lifestyle factors significantly influence attitude, social influence, self-efficacy, situational factors, and environmental concern, as well as behaviour to reduce food waste*.

3. Method and material

3.1. Participants

The purposive sampling technique was used for recruiting 432 respondents from Danish university canteens. A poster containing information about the Project was designed, such as a QR code directing to the questionnaire developed in the Survey Exact platform. The poster was posted on the canteens' social media page, and printed copies were attached to the information board of the university canteens. The survey was activated from 16th May 2022 till 30th September 2022. However, the survey was deactivated due to the summer holidays between 1st July

and 15th August 2022. Informed consent was taken from all participants before filling in the survey. The respondents who did not provide informed consent were directed to end the survey and could not participate.

Furthermore, all participants were notified regarding the duration (approximately 6 – 7 minutes) to complete the survey beforehand. Since the survey was conducted at the university canteen, no minors were involved, and university canteen users aged 18 and above were recruited. This study followed the Declaration of Helsinki and obtained approval from the Research Ethics Committee of Science and Health at the University of Copenhagen (Journal no.: 504-0331/22-5000).

3.2. Questionnaire

The questionnaire was developed and distributed in the English language. The questions measuring the constructs of the proposed extended-ASE framework (Fig. 1) were adopted from previous studies (Table 1). The questionnaire was divided into three sections consisting of 22 closed questions with 48 variables. The first section explored respondents' food choice motives on a typical day. The food choice motives questionnaire was adjusted by reducing nine factors – 36 items to seven factors – 13 items. The selected factors were Health (2 items), Mood (1), Sensory appeal (3), Natural content (1), Price (2), Weight control (2), and Familiarity (2) (see Table 1). The selection of the food choice motive factors and items was inspired by previous studies on food waste (Teng et al., 2022), with adjustments relevant to this study's purpose. The items were assessed using a 7-point Likert scale ranging from "not important at all" to "extremely important".

The second section measured the constructs from the ASE framework, situational factors, and environmental concern. The respondents were asked to report their responses using a 7-point Likert scale ranging from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree". Attitude, social influence, self-efficacy, intention, situational factors, and environmental concern were measured with three items each. Behaviour was measured with two items. The first item measuring food waste behaviour was 'How often did you generate food waste at lunch in the last week?'; ranging from "never" to "almost always". The second item was 'How likely is it that you had following among of plate waste at your lunch yesterday?'. It was measured by visualising small clipart ranging from "no plate waste" to "total plate waste" (see Fig. 2).

The third section measured respondents' sociodemographic and lifestyle factors. Age (in years), gender (male, female), living status (alone, with a partner, within a partner and children, single parent, with a parent, with a roommate, others), education (intermediate, bachelor, master, PhD, other), employment status (student, student with a job, part-time job, full-time job, self-employed, unemployed), monthly income after tax (0–20,000 DKK, 20001–40000 DKK, 40001–60000 DKK, 60001–80000 DKK, 80001–100000 DKK, 100,001 DKK and above, prefer not to answer), region of residence (Capital region, region Zealand, central Denmark region, north Denmark region), grocery shopping (>50 % of the shopping, 50 % of the shopping, sometimes, never), dietary pattern (omnivore, vegetarian, flexitarian, vegan), height (meter), and weight (kilogram) were taken.

3.3. Data analysis

The statistical analysis was done in IBM SPSS version 28.0 (IBM Corp, 2013) using an Excel file transferred from the Survey-Xact platform. Initially, Body mass index (BMI) was calculated as weight (kg)/height (m²). BMI was categorised using the World Health Organization cut-off values for BMI, where underweight was defined as <18.5 kg/m², normal as 18.50 – 24.99 kg/m², overweight ≥ 25 kg/m², obese ≥ 30 kg/m² (World Health Organization, 2022). All reversed scale questions were reported similarly. Descriptive statistics were conducted for the food choice motives presented as mean and standard deviation. Further, principal component analysis selecting eigenvalues > 1 was conducted

Fig. 1. A proposed extended-ASE framework for identifying factors influencing food waste-reducing behaviour at the university canteen.

to investigate the variability and interrelationships among the food choice motives factors. The suitability of the data for factor analysis was assessed using the Kaiser, Meyer and Olkin test. Further, the loading of the food choice motives was ranked based on the calculation using their aggregated mean scores. Their differences were determined using Kendall's W test. Cluster analysis was performed using hierarchical cluster analysis to estimate the number of segments. The similarity between the objects was measured with a squared Euclidean distance, and the segments were yielded by aggregating the objects using Ward's method. The ANOVA, Chi-square, and Kruskal-Wallis H tests were used to compare the segments' sociodemographic and lifestyle factors.

Confirmatory factor analysis was performed for the proposed extended-ASE framework. Cronbach's α and variance inflation factor (VIF) were used to evaluate the reliability and multicollinearity, respectively. Partial least squares structural equation modelling (PLS-SEM) was employed to explain complex relationships between the constructs using WarpPLS software version 8.0 (Kock, 2022b). The hypothesis was tested using a default outer model algorithm PLS regression routine with a default inner model analysis (Warp 3 algorithm) and the bootstrapping resampling method (number of data resamples = 999). Lastly, to evaluate the model fit, the eight commonly used measures of goodness-of-fit (GoF) were selected: (1) average path coefficient (APC), (2) average r-squared (ARS), (3) average variance inflation factors (AVIF), (4) average full collinearity (AFVIF), (5) Tenenhaus GoF, (6) Sympton's paradox ratio, (7) R-squared contribution ratio, and (8) nonlinear bivariate causality direction ratio (Kock, 2022a; Hair et al., 2011; Henseler & Sarstedt, 2013).

4. Result

4.1. Food choice motives

The results from the descriptive statistics and exploratory factor analysis are shown in Table 2. The result from the principal component analysis revealed five food choice motive factors: (1) sensory appeal, (2) price, (3) weight control, (4) familiarity, and (5) health and mood. The factors together accounted for 73.062 % of the variance in the items where the Kaiser, Meyer and Olkin measure of sampling adequacy yielded a value of 0.647***, implying the appropriateness of factor analysis (Malhotra, 2010).

4.1.1. Aggregated mean scores

Fig. 3 shows five food choice motive factors ranked based on the calculation using aggregated mean scores for all item loadings. In line with the ranking stated by (Glanz et al., 1998; Steptoe et al., 1995), sensory appeal was the most dominant, and familiarity was the least essential food choice motive factor among the consumers. The aggregated mean scores were almost identical for price, health and mood, followed by weight control. Moreover, there was a significant difference (Kendall's W = 0.529, $P = <0.001$) in the importance of these factors.

4.1.2. Consumer segments and their characteristics

Factor scores of the five identified food choice motives were used for the hierarchical cluster analysis. Fig. 4 shows the factor loadings of the segment. Four consumer segments were generated from food choice motives. The consumers' food choices in cluster 1 were primarily influenced by familiarity and may therefore be described as "Familiarity sensitive consumers". Consumers in cluster 2 were somewhat concerned by the sensory appeal and price, while familiarity, weight control, health and mood were unimportant. Cluster 2 was called "Unconcerned consumers". Consumers in cluster 3 reported the lowest scores on weight control, price, sensory appeal, and familiarity, but health and mood were important. Cluster 3 was called "Food for health and mood consumers". Consumers in cluster 4 were less concerned by familiarity and more concerned by weight control, followed by health and mood, price, and, finally, sensory appeal. Cluster 4 was called "Unfamiliar Consumers". Cluster 1 is the largest group identified in the study, including 34.9 % of the sample, followed by Cluster 4 (26 %), Cluster 2 (19.9 %), and Cluster 3 (19.2 %).

The sociodemographic and lifestyle factors of the consumer segments are shown in Table 3. A total of 438 complete responses were included in the analysis, where the average age was 28 years old, with the majority of the respondents being female (67.1 %). Most of the respondents were a student with a job (42.5 %) residing in the capital region of Copenhagen (58.9 %) with an average income of 20,000 DKK (44.5 %). Further, 65.1 % of the respondents followed the omnivore diet reporting normal BMI (64.4 %), whereas the majority did the grocery shopping themselves (54.8 %). Except for gender, all considered sociodemographic and lifestyle factors (age, education, living status, employment status, income, household shopping, region of residence, dietary pattern, and body mass index) are significantly different between the four consumer segments.

Table 1
Items for measuring the constructs of the proposed extended-ASE framework.

Constructs	Items	Source of adoption
Food choice motives	Item 1: Smells nice Item 2: It has a pleasant texture Item 3: Tastes good Item 4: Is good value for money Item 5: Is cheap Item 6: It is what I usually eat Item 7: Is familiar Item 8: Keeps me healthy Item 9: Is nutritious Item 10: It makes me feel good Item 11: Contains natural ingredients Item 12: It helps me control my weight Item 13: It is low in fat	(Steeptoe et al., 1995)
Attitude (ATT)	ATT1: Reducing food waste will have a positive effect on environmental protection. ATT2: Reducing food waste is helping to improve the quality of life. ATT3: Reducing food waste is a wise move.	(Tsai et al., 2020)
Social influence (SOC)	SI1: People who are important to me approve if I generate food waste. SI2: People who are important to me find it desirable if I generate food waste. SI3: People who are important to me think it is necessary to reduce the amount of food waste.	(Chen, 2022; Stefan et al., 2013)
Self-efficacy (SEE)	SE1: Whether or not to waste food fully depends on me. SE2: I won't leave food on my plate, even if I don't like it. SE3: I am better at reducing food waste than people my age.	(Tsai et al., 2020)
Intention (INT)	INT1: I intend to eat all the food that I have taken myself. INT2: I'm willing to reduce food waste on my plate. INT3: I'm willing to reduce environmental damage through my actions.	(Bell & Ulhas, 2020; Tsai et al., 2020)
Behaviour (BEH)	BEH1: How often did you generate food waste at lunch in the last week? BEH2: Amount of plate waste at your lunch yesterday (see Fig. 2).	(Bell & Ulhas, 2020; Ellison et al., 2019)
Situational factors (SIT)	SIT1: If I leave food, it is because I'm full. SIT2: If I leave food, it is because I don't like it. SIT3: If I leave food, it is because I'm in a hurry.	(Bell & Ulhas, 2020; Laven, 2017)
Environmental concern (ENC)	ENC1: I am concerned about the impact of food waste on climate change. ENC2: I am concerned about the impact of food waste on the ecosystem. ENC3: I am concerned about the emission of greenhouse gases from food waste.	(Bell & Ulhas, 2020; Kim & Hall, 2019)

4.2. Proposed extended-ASE framework

4.2.1. Confirmatory factor analysis, validity, reliability, and multicollinearity tests

The results from confirmatory factor analysis measuring constructs from the proposed extended-ASE framework are shown in Table 4. The result indicates acceptable convergent validity as the normalised structure loadings for each construct were reported above 0.63. Moreover, the value of Cronbach's α was reported above 0.60, indicating high reliability and acceptable index among the items of the constructs (Pallant, 2020). The average variance extracted (AVE) for each construct was reported above 0.56, where above the minimum threshold of 0.50, signifying convergent validity. The value of VIF was reported below the maximum threshold of 3.3, indicating no multicollinearity (Bowerman and O'Connell, 2000). Further, the square roots of the AVE of the construct were greater than the correlation coefficient among the constructs (see Table 5), which confirmed the discriminant validity of the constructs validity (Hair et al., 2022).

4.2.2. Goodness-of-fit statistics

The goodness-of-fit shown in Table 6 indicates that the proposed extended-ASE framework has a better predictive power of Intention ($R^2 = 0.481$) and behaviour ($R^2 = 0.259$) when compared to the original ASE framework. Further, a better predictive power of attitude ($R^2 = 0.269$) was attained by including food choice motives and sociodemographic and lifestyle factors in the framework. Moreover, the proposed extended ASE framework reported AVIF = 1.369, AFVIF = 1.559, and nonlinear bivariate causality direction ratio = 0.954, representing a good model fit (Tenenhaus et al., 2004). Therefore, the proposed extended-ASE framework with situational factors, environmental concern, food choice motives, and sociodemographic and lifestyle factors was retrained to perform PLS-SEM analysis.

4.2.3. PLS-SEM analysis

The result from the path analysis of the proposed extended-ASE framework is shown in Table 7. Among the constructs of the ASE framework, attitude ($\beta = 0.336, p < 0.001, \text{Cohen's } f^2 = 0.202$) and self-efficacy ($\beta = 0.140, p < 0.001, \text{Cohen's } f^2 = 0.053$) significantly influenced behavioural intention reporting medium and small effect sizes, respectively. However, social influence ($\beta = 0.048, p = 0.218, \text{Cohen's } f^2 = 0.011$) had no significant influence on behavioural intention. Further, behavioural intention mediates the relationship between motivational factors and food waste behaviour ($\beta = 0.212, p = 0.004, \text{Cohen's } f^2 = 0.056$), but a small effect size was noted. Thus, hypotheses H1, H3, and H4 were supported, while H2 was rejected. The situational factor ($\beta = -0.071, p = 0.053, \text{Cohen's } f^2 = 0.011$) had no significant influence on behavioural intention; thus, H5 was rejected. Finally, environmental concern ($\beta = 0.333, p < 0.001, \text{Cohen's } f^2 = 0.204$) significantly influenced behavioural intention with a medium effect size to support H6.

Table 8a and 8b shows the relationship between background factors and the constructs of the proposed extended-ASE framework. All factors from the food choice motives, sensory appeal ($\beta = -0.203, p = 0.036$),

How likely is it that you had following amount of plate waste at your lunch yesterday?

Fig. 2. One of the items measuring respondent's plate waste behaviour.

Table 2
Mean, standard deviation and factor analysis of the item measuring food choice motives.

Item	Mean ± SD	Sensory appeal	Price	Weight control	Familiarity	Health and mood
Smells nice	5.59 ± 1.182	0.788				
It has a pleasant texture	5.55 ± 1.229	0.782				
Tastes good	6.45 ± 0.878	0.615				
Is good value for money	5.97 ± 1.096		0.830			
Is cheap	5.10 ± 1.368		0.871			
It is what I usually eat	2.74 ± 1.555				0.907	
Is familiar	2.97 ± 1.608				0.895	
Keeps me healthy	5.37 ± 1.351					0.757
Is nutritious	5.55 ± 1.213					0.749
It makes me feel good	5.75 ± 1.176					0.657
Contains natural ingredients	5.03 ± 1.406					0.690
It helps me control my weight	4.32 ± 1.773			0.841		
It is low in fat	3.65 ± 1.668			0.799		

SD = Standard deviation.

Fig. 3. Aggregated mean scores for ranking of food choice motive factors.

Fig. 4. Factor loadings of the clusters.

price ($\beta = 0.201, p = 0.001$), familiarity ($\beta = -0.200, p = <0.001$), and health and mood ($\beta = 0.287, p = <0.001$), except weight control ($\beta = 0.030, p = 0.330$) had a significant influence on attitude towards reduced food waste. Thus, supporting H7a, H7b, H7d and H7e but rejecting H7c. Further, food choice motives, weight control ($\beta = 0.222, p = <0.001$), and familiarity ($\beta = -0.206, p = <0.001$) had a significant influence on reducing food waste behaviour while sensory appeal ($\beta = 0.121, p = 0.265$), price ($\beta = 0.166, p = 0.124$), and health and mood ($\beta = 0.032, p = 0.339$) had no significant influence on reducing food waste behaviour. Thus, supporting H8c, and H8d.

The result from path analysis of sociodemographic factors and

lifestyle factors shows that age had a highly significant influence on self-efficacy ($\beta = 0.295, p = <0.001$) and environmental concern ($\beta = 0.195, p = <0.001$), supporting hypotheses H11a and H13a. Further, gender had an influence on attitude ($\beta = 0.097, p = 0.014$), social influence ($\beta = 0.153, p = <0.001$), self-efficacy ($\beta = -0.195, p = 0.001$) and environmental concern ($\beta = 0.156, p = 0.002$), supporting hypotheses H9b, H10b, H11b and H13b. Living status influenced situational factors ($\beta = -0.114, p = 0.024$) and environmental concern ($\beta = -0.142, p = 0.005$); thus, hypotheses H12c and H13c were supported. Further, education influenced all the constructs of the extended ASE framework supporting hypotheses H9d, H10d, H11d, H12d, H13d, and H14d. Employment had

Table 3
Sociodemographic and lifestyle factors of the segments and their differences.

%(n)	Familiarity sensitive consumers (n = 153)	Unconcerned consumers (n = 87)	Food for health and mood consumers (n = 84)	Unfamiliarity consumers (n = 114)	Overall sample (n = 438)	p-value
Age, y, mean ± SD	27.41 ± 9.33	26.34 ± 6.54	30.93 ± 9.75	28.89 ± 11.68	28.26 ± 9.72	0.010 ^a
Gender	27.5	37.9	32.1	36.8	32.9	0.275 ^b
Male	(42)72.5	(33)62.1	(27)67.9	(42)63.2	(144)67.1	
Female	(111)	(54)	(57)	(72)	(294)	
Living status	25.5	27.6	17.9	21.1	23.3	<0.001 ^b
Alone	(39)25.5	(24)24.1	(15)28.6	(24)28.9	(102)26.7	
With a partner	(39)5.9	(21)10.3	(24)25	(33)23.7	(117)15.1	
With a partner and children	(9)3.9	(9)3.4	(21)	(27)	(66)2.1	
Single parent	(6)7.8	(3)3.4	-3.6	-2.6	(9)4.8	
With a parent	(12)29.4	(3)31	(3)21.4	(3)15.8	(21)24.7	
With a roommate(s)	(45)2	(27)	(18)3.6	(18)7.9	(108)3.4	
Other	(3)	-	(3)	(9)	(15)	
Education	33.3	48.3	25	36.8	35.6	0.001 ^c
Intermediate	(51)41.2	(42)27.6	(21)32.1	(42)23.7	(156)32.2	
Bachelor	(63)21.6	(24)20.7	(27)21.4	(27)21.1	(141)21.2	
Master	(33)2.0	(18)	(18)14.3	(24)15.8	(93)7.5	
PhD	(3)2.0	-3.4	(12)7.1	(18)2.6	(33)3.4	
Other	(3)	(3)	(6)	(3)	(15)	
Employment status	29.4	31	17.9	36.8	29.5	<0.001 ^c
Student	(45)51	(27)55.2	(15)32.1	(42)28.9	(129)42.5	
Student with a job	(78)	(48)	(27)7.1	(33)	(186)1.4	
Part-time job	-19.6	-13.8	(6)42.9	-28.9	(6)25.3	
Full-time job	(30)	(12)	(36)	(33)2.6	(111)0.7	
Self-employed	-	-	-	(3)2.6	(3)0.7	
Unemployed	-	-	-	(3)	(3)	
Income	54.9	58.6	21.4	36.8	44.5	<0.001 ^c
0–20,000 DKK	(84)13.7	(51)24.1	(18)25	(42)15.8	(195)18.5	
20,001–40,000 DKK	(21)7.8	(21)3.4	(21)21.4	(18)15.8	(81)11.6	
40,001–60,000 DKK	(12)3.9	(3)6.9	(18)21.4	(18)7.9	(51)8.9	
60,001–80,000 DKK	(6)2	(6)3.4	(18)7.1	(9)5.3	(39)4.1	
80,001–100,000 DKK	(3)2	(3)3.4	(6)3.6	(6)7.9	(18)4.1	
100,001 DKK and above	(3)15.7	(3)	(3)	(9)10.5	(18)8.2	
Prefer not to answer	(24)	-	-	(12)	(36)	
Region of residence	45.1	65.5	64.3	68.4	58.9	<0.001 ^b
Capital Region	(69)11.8	(57)3.4	(54)17.9	(78)	(258)8.2	
Region Zealand	(18)41.2	(3)31	(15)14.3	-28.9	(36)30.8	
Central Denmark Region	(63)2.0	(27)	(12)3.6	(33)2.6	(135)2.1	
North Denmark Region	(3)	-	(3)	(3)	(9)	
Grocery shopping	64.7	44.8	46.4	55.3	54.8	0.003 ^b
>50 % of the shopping	(99)27.5	(39)31	(39)35.7	(63)31.6	(240)30.8	
50%	(42)5.9	(27)24.1	(30)14.3	(36)10.5	(135)12.3	
Sometimes	(9)2	(21)	(12)3.6	(12)2.6	(54)2.1	
Never	(3)	-	(3)	(3)	(9)	
Dietary pattern	68.6	69	50	68.4	65.1	0.006 ^b
Omnivore	(105)9.8	(60)13.8	(42)17.9	(78)10.5	(285)12.3	
Vegetarian	(15)19.6	(12)17.2	(15)25	(12)21.1	(54)20.5	
Flexitarian	(30)2	(15)	(21)7.1	(24)	(90)2.1	
Vegan	(3)	-	(6)	-	(9)	
BMI (kg/m ²)	2	3.6	3.6	5.3	2.7	<0.001 ^c
Underweight (Below 18.5)	(3)70.6	-62.1	(3)78.6	(6)47.4	(12)64.4	
Normal weight	(108)	(54)	(66)	(54)	(282)	
Overweight (18.5–24.9)	23.5(36)3.9	32.2(28)5.7	17.9(15)	36.8(42)10.5	27.6(121)5.3	
Obesity (25.0–29.9 and above)	(6)	(5)	-	(12)	(23)	

^a ANOVA, ^bChi-square, ^cKruskal-Wallis H test, SD = Standard Deviation, BMI = Body mass index.

an influence on social influence ($\beta = -0.212$, $p = <0.001$), situational factor ($\beta = -0.129$, $p = 0.020$) and environmental concern ($\beta = -0.110$, $p = 0.033$), thus, H10e, H12e, and H13e were supported. Further, income influenced self-efficacy ($\beta = -0.093$, $p = 0.041$), and behaviour ($\beta = -0.166$, $p = <0.001$) whereas shopping only influenced self-efficacy ($\beta = 0.132$, $p = 0.005$), supporting hypotheses H11f, H14f, and H11g were supported, respectively. Both residence ($\beta = 0.126$, $p = 0.005$) and dietary pattern ($\beta = -0.104$, $p = 0.014$) influenced environmental concern, whereas dietary pattern also influenced behaviour ($\beta = 0.159$, $p = 0.001$), thus supporting H13h, H13i and H14i, respectively. Lastly, BMI had an influence on attitude ($\beta = -0.153$, $p = <0.001$), situational factor ($\beta = -0.128$, $p = 0.004$), environmental concern ($\beta = -0.102$, $p = 0.011$) and behaviour ($\beta = 0.088$, $p = 0.01$), supporting hypotheses H9j, H12j,

H13j and H14j (see Table 8a and 8b).

5. Discussion

The study aimed to segment consumers based on food choice motives and understand key factors influencing consumers' food waste reduction behaviour through applying an ASE framework extended with situational factors, environmental concerns, and background factors (food choice motives, sociodemographic, and lifestyle factors). The findings from this study identified four consumer segments based on their food choice motives, (1) Familiarity sensitive consumers, (2) Unconcerned consumers, (3) Food for health and mood consumers, and (4) Unfamiliar consumers. Further, this study confirmed the adequacy of the ASE

Table 4
Confirmatory factor analysis, validity, reliability, and multicollinearity tests.

Constructs	Items	Median (IQR)	Normalised structure loadings	Cronbach's α	AVE	CRC	VIF
Attitude (ATT)	ATT1	7(1)6	0.683	0.851	0.771	0.910	1.998
	ATT2	(2)7	0.630				
	ATT3	(1)	0.665				
Social Influence (SOC)	SOC1	4(3)3	0.849	0.670	0.608	0.821	1.385
	SOC2	(2)5	0.774				
	SOC3	(2)	0.708				
Self-efficacy (SEE)	SEE1	5(3)4	0.671	0.612	0.566	0.795	1.516
	SEE2	(3)4	0.764				
	SEE3	(2)	0.739				
Situational factor (SIT)	SIT1	5(2.25)3	0.868	0.604	0.558	0.791	1.151
	SIT2	(3)4	0.919				
	SIT3	(3)	0.908				
Environmental concern (ENC)	ENC1	6(2)6	0.656	0.929	0.876	0.955	2.098
	ENC2	(2)6	0.681				
	ENC3	(1)	0.660				
Intention (INT)	INT1	6(1)6	0.645	0.817	0.732	0.891	2.104
	INT2	(1)6	0.656				
	INT3	(1)	0.645				
Behaviour (BEH)	BEH1	5(1)6	0.847	0.603	0.716	0.834	1.317
	BEH2	(1)	0.858				
Sensory appeal (SA)	SA1	6(1)6	0.893	0.622	0.571	0.799	1.258
	SA2	(1)7	0.919				
	SA3	(1)	0.807				
Price (PR)	PR1	6(2)5	0.769	0.696	0.767	0.868	1.513
	PR2	(2)	0.728				
Familiarity (FM)	FM1	2(3)3	0.836	0.834	0.858	0.923	1.382
	FM2	(2)	0.871				
Health and mood (HM)	HM1	6(1)6	0.698	0.760	0.594	0.850	1.854
	HM2	(1)6	0.697				
	HM3	(1)5	0.690				
	HM4	(2)	0.733				
Weight control (WC)	WC1	4(3)4	0.802	0.780	0.820	0.901	1.614
	WC2	(3)	0.770				

IQR = Interquartile range, AVE = average variance extracted, CRC = composite reliability, VIF = variance inflation factor.

Table 5
Correlations among the constructs with square roots of average variance extracted.

Constructs	ATT	SOC	SEE	SIT	ENC	INT	BEH
Attitude (ATT)	0.874						
Social influence (SOC)	0.156**	0.780					
Self-efficacy (SEE)	0.311***	0.055	0.752				
Situational factors (SIT)	-0.070	-0.036	0.051	0.747			
Environmental concern (ENC)	0.568***	0.180***	0.395***	0.061	0.936		
Intention (INT)	0.566***	0.131**	0.369***	-0.083	0.565***	0.855	
Behaviour (BEH)	0.230***	-0.103*	0.099*	-0.033	0.126***	0.245***	0.846

*significant at $p < 0.05$, **significant at $p < 0.01$, ***significant at $p < 0.001$, bold numbers are the square root values of average variance extracted (AVE).

framework for understanding food waste reduction behaviour among canteen users. Furthermore, the extension of the ASE framework with food choice motives, situational factors, environmental concern, and sociodemographic and lifestyle factors increased the explained variance of attitude and behaviour.

The finding of this study shows that attitude was the most significant predictor for food waste reduction intention, while Russell et al. (2017) found that attitude was not a significant predictor of intention to reduce food waste among UK consumers. However, the attitude was a significant predictor of household food waste behaviour in Denmark (Stancu et al., 2016) and other countries (Abeliotis et al., 2014; Graham-Rowe et al., 2015; Stefan et al., 2013; Wang et al., 2023; Wong, 2019). Danish consumers generally have a positive attitude toward reducing food waste, which might be due to ongoing nationwide campaigns on food waste reduction (Stop wasting food, 2023; Szulecka et al., 2019). Furthermore, consumer willingness to take action to support these initiatives shows their positive attitudes toward social responsibility in promoting more sustainable and responsible food consumption. Previous studies have shown that information campaigns to promote consumer attitude had up to 28 % food waste reduction, thus, such

campaigns should be considered as a priority for food waste reduction in canteens (Reynolds et al., 2019). Further, such campaigns might target the Food for health and mood consumer segment for a larger effect on behavioural attitude.

The findings from this study suggest that self-efficacy was a significant predictor of intention to reduce food waste, which aligns with previous studies' findings (Aschemann-Witzel et al., 2020; Kim et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2022). When individuals have higher self-efficacy toward reducing food waste, they are more likely to acknowledge their contribution to addressing environmental problems and feel a sense of ability to motivate others to reduce food waste (Wang et al., 2022). Thus, the canteen operators should work on stakeholder engagement (Kolawole et al., 2021) while promoting both consumers' self-efficacy and perceived collective efficacy towards reducing food waste. For instance, canteens may use message-framing strategies to influence consumer perception of the food waste management efforts of canteens (Huang et al., 2021). When consumers perceive the food waste reduction efforts made by canteens, they may feel more capable of being involved in canteen-generated food waste reduction initiatives, resulting in behavioural intentions and self-engagement in reducing food waste

Table 6
Goodness-of-fit statistics of the proposed extended-ASE framework.

	ASE framework ^a	ASE framework extended with situational factors and environmental concern	ASE framework extended with situational factors, environmental concerns, food choice motives, and sociodemographic and lifestyle factors	Standard norms ^b
APC	0.272***	0.199***	0.102***	
ARS	0.240***	0.275***	0.205**	
AVIF	1.112	1.336	1.369	≤3.3
AFVIF	1.296	1.405	1.559	≤3.3
Tenenhaus GoF	0.403	0.435	0.414	≥0.36 large
Sympson's paradox ratio	1.000	1.000	0.882	≥0.7
R-squared contribution ratio	1.000	1.000	0.995	≥0.9
Nonlinear bivariate causality direction ratio	0.875	0.833	0.954	≥0.7
R ² attitude	–	–	0.269	
R ² intention	0.410	0.481	0.481	
R ² behaviour	0.070	0.070	0.259	
Q ² attitude	–	–	0.263	
Q ² intention	0.404	0.475	0.475	
Q ² behaviour	0.069	0.069	0.263	

^a Original ASE framework = Direct path from attitude, social influence, and self-efficacy to intention, eventually influencing behaviour. ^b Source: (Tenenhaus et al., 2004). APC = average path coefficient, ARS = average r-squared, AVIF = average variance inflation factors, AFVIF = average full collinearity.

Table 7
Path analysis of the proposed extended-ASE framework and hypothesis status.

Paths	Standardised estimates	Standard Error	Cohen's f ²	P-value	Hypothesis status
ATT to INT	0.336	0.094	0.202	<0.001	H1 – Supported
SOC to INT	0.048	0.061	0.011	0.218	H2 – Rejected
SEE to INT	0.140	0.043	0.053	<0.001	H3 – Supported
INT to BEH	0.212	0.080	0.056	0.004	H4 – Supported
SIT to INT	–0.071	0.044	0.011	0.053	H5 – Rejected
ENC to INT	0.333	0.084	0.204	<0.001	H6 – Supported

ATT = attitudes, SOC = social influence, SEE = self-efficacy, SIT = situational factors, ENC = environmental concern, INT = intention, and BEH = behaviour.

Table 8a
Relationships between the background factors and attitude, and behavior.

Background factors	H7: Attitude		H8: Behavior	
	Coeff	P	Coeff	P
Food choice motives				
a) Sensory appeal	–0.203	0.036	0.121	0.265
b) Price	0.201	0.001	0.166	0.124
c) Weight control	0.030	0.330	0.222	<0.001
d) Familiarity	–0.200	<0.001	–0.206	<0.001
e) Health–Mood	0.287	<0.001	0.032	0.339
Sociodemographic and lifestyle factors				
	H9: Attitude		H14: Behavior	
	Coeff	P	Coeff	P
a) Age (Under 25 = 1)	0.040	0.218	–0.044	0.186
b) Gender (Male = 1)	0.097	0.014	–0.072	0.062
c) Living status (Alone = 1)	0.032	0.246	0.080	0.065
d) Education (Bachelor and above = 1)	0.087	0.018	–0.199	<0.001
e) Employment (Fulltime = 1)	–0.024	0.324	–0.025	0.326
f) Income (≥20,000 = 1)	0.022	0.327	–0.166	<0.001
g) Shopping (>50 % of the shopping = 1)	0.038	0.208	–0.019	0.357
h) Residence (Capital region = 1)	0.052	0.115	–0.044	0.177
i) Dietary pattern (Omnivore = 1)	0.073	0.065	0.159	0.001
j) BMI (Normal = 1)	–0.153	<0.001	0.088	0.014

(Ding & Jiang, 2023). Further, such initiatives should target consumers' sociodemographic factors, age, gender, education, income, and shopping patterns to effectively enhance their self-efficacy.

Further, environmental concern was a significant predictor of intention to reduce food waste, supporting recent research conducted in a cafeteria setting in Taiwan (Bell & Ulhas, 2020). Consumers who are more aware of the environmental consequences of food waste and those who know how it contributes to climate change are more motivated to take action and intend to reduce their food waste (Rosenlund et al., 2020). This study found that age, gender, living status, education, employment status, dietary pattern, residence, and body mass index influence their perception towards environmental concern. Therefore, a marketing campaign could be launched in university canteens to make consumers aware of the impacts of food waste on climate change, eventually affecting behavioural intention to promote food waste reduction behaviour.

Social influence was not a significant predictor for intention to reduce food waste which is in line with the findings from a previous study conducted in a Chinese canteen (Tsai et al., 2020). This might be because food waste is an unconscious decision and eating is characterised by habit and rituals, thus, much less influenced by social norms (Questa et al., 2013). Further, even though previous research has associated appetite, level of hunger and time constraints as situational factors resulting in food waste, this study opposes the findings (Laven, 2017; Miroso et al., 2016; Schneider, 2008, Bell & Ulhas, 2020). In this study, the data collection was conducted just before and after summer vacation, therefore, it is usually not a busy period at the canteen which might have resulted in no significance of situational factors on intention to reduce food waste. In contrast, Fraj-Andrés et al. (2023) identified situational factors influencing food waste behaviours in various circumstances, including family size and employment status.

Adding food choice motives enriches the application of the ASE framework in explaining canteen consumers' attitudes and behaviour on reducing food waste in out-of-home dining settings. This study's four food choice motives (sensory appeal, price, familiarity, and health–mood) significantly influence consumers' attitudes toward reducing food waste. While weight control and familiarity had a direct and significant influence on behaviour. Further, body mass index had a significant influence on behaviour towards reducing food waste indicating that consumers with normal body weight tend to reduce food waste in university canteen. In contrast, a previous study found that weight did not significantly influence food waste behaviour (Sheen et al., 2020). Therefore, supported by the ASE framework, the findings from this study can serve as a systematic and holistic picture in designing and

Table 8b

Relationships between the sociodemographic, and lifestyle factors and the remaining constructs: social influence (SOC), self-efficacy (SEE), situational (SIT), and environmental concern (ENC).

Sociodemographic and lifestyle factors	H10: SOC		H11: SEE		H12: SIT		H13: ENC	
	Coeff	P	Coeff	P	Coeff	P	Coeff	P
a) Age (Under 25 = 1)	-0.004	0.467	0.295	<0.001	-0.018	0.376	0.195	<0.001
b) Gender (Male = 1)	0.153	<0.001	-0.195	0.001	0.030	0.289	0.156	0.002
c) Living status (Alone = 1)	-0.008	0.440	-0.042	0.240	-0.114	0.024	-0.142	0.005
d) Education (Bachelor and above = 1)	-0.108	0.022	0.111	0.015	-0.081	0.074	0.189	<0.001
e) Employment (Fulltime = 1)	-0.212	<0.001	-0.012	0.421	-0.129	0.020	0.110	0.033
f) Income ($\geq 20,000 = 1$)	0.051	0.188	-0.093	0.041	-0.006	0.457	0.078	0.081
g) Shopping ($>50\%$ of the shopping = 1)	-0.020	0.357	0.132	0.005	-0.030	0.291	-0.002	0.485
h) Residence (Capital region = 1)	0.039	0.216	0.032	0.257	-0.008	0.437	0.126	0.005
i) Dietary pattern (Omnivore = 1)	-0.079	0.055	-0.056	0.134	-0.079	0.050	-0.104	0.014
j) BMI (Normal = 1)	-0.025	0.308	0.068	0.071	-0.128	0.004	-0.102	0.011

developing food waste reduction interventions in university canteens. For instance, communicating the benefits of food waste reduction (e.g., on the environment, and quality of life), enhancing the sensory appeal and familiarity, and paying extra attention to price, health-mood and weight control factors might influence consumers' behaviour towards reducing food waste.

Lastly, intention, sociodemographic and lifestyle factors, education, income, dietary pattern and BMI seem to influence food waste reduction behaviour. The findings from this study indicate that consumers' motivation does not accord perfectly with their behaviour – an intention-behaviour gap (Sheeran, 2005). In addition, food waste reduction behaviour is habitual in nature; consumers may find it difficult to act on their good intentions. Thus, previous studies have suggested considering some potential moderators of the intention-behaviour gap, such as contextual and habitual factors (Fan et al., 2019; Fraj-Andrés et al., 2023; Russell et al., 2017) concerning food waste reduction behaviour. Thus, food waste reduction intervention should integrate contextual and habitual factors to reduce the intention-behaviour gap. Further studies are warranted to understand how habit strength may moderate food waste reduction behaviour.

Interestingly, consumers with higher education were reported to have higher food waste behaviour indicating that people with high education tend to have higher incomes and thus are more likely to over-purchase and discard food (Monier, 2011). In addition, food waste behaviour among consumer with higher education and higher income were reported in previous studies (Secondi et al., 2015; Stefan et al., 2013). Consumers with normal BMI reported positive behaviour towards reducing food waste. It aligns with the findings from previous research where individuals with high BMI are less concerned about the consequences of food waste (Woo, 2014). Lastly, consumers following the omnivore diet were associated with reduced food waste behaviour. However, a recent study in a Danish canteen reported a negative association between omnivore dietary patterns and surplus meal-buying behaviour (Pandey et al., 2023).

There are several limitations to this study. First, the study limits the generalizability of the findings due to the small sample size that may not represent the larger population. However, the study does fulfil the minimum sample size requirement ("10-times rule") for conducting PLS-SEM (Hair et al., 2011). Further, the cross-sectional data limits the causal inference of the findings, which may limit the validity of the results. The study was based on their self-reported questionnaire, which may have resulted in self-reporting, social desirability, and recall biases (Althubaiti, 2016). Moreover, the sample was biased in terms of respondents mostly females living in the capital region of Copenhagen. Other relevant psychosocial factors such as habit, and self-identity as well as sociodemographic and lifestyle factors such as religion, and country of origin might have strengthened the understanding of consumers' food waste reduction behaviour. Finally, the study used a brief measure of food choice motives questionnaire (Steptoe et al., 1995) and thus may have limited more precise estimations of consumer food choice

motives. However, a shorter version of the food choice motives questionnaire has proven to be a reliable alternative for the multi-item scale (Onwezen et al., 2019).

6. Conclusion

In conclusion, this exploratory study presents a market segmentation of Danish canteen users differentiated by food choice motives that comprised four segments: the "Familiarity sensitive consumers", the "Unconcerned consumers", the "Food for health and mood consumers", and the "Unfamiliar consumers". Consumers' food waste reduction behaviour was analysed using an extended ASE framework to understand better the factors influencing food waste reduction behaviour. The findings from this study indicate that it is possible to influence consumers' food waste-reducing behaviour with their intentions to reduce food waste, which can further be influenced through attitudes, self-efficacy, and environmental concern. Price, health-mood, sensory appeal, and familiarity influenced consumers' attitudes, while familiarity and weight control were directly influencing consumers' behaviour. Sociodemographic and lifestyle factors, age, gender, living status, education, employment, income, shopping, residence, dietary pattern, and BMI indirectly influence behavioural intention by affecting attitudes, self-efficacy, and environmental concern. While, education, income, dietary patterns, and BMI directly influenced consumers' food waste reduction behaviour.

Therefore, food waste practitioners should consider developing attitude-efficacy-building programmes along with making consumers aware of the environmental benefits of reducing food waste. Improving food familiarity through adding meal descriptions, hosting tasting events to gradually introduce new dishes, and integrating it with nutritional intervention could be effective in reducing food waste. Further, allowing the consumer to weigh their canteen meal before purchasing could potentially reduce food waste. Such strategies could be effective when targeted to the 'Familiarity sensitive', 'Food for health and mood', and 'Unfamiliarity' consumer segments. Tailored interventions for the 'Food for health and mood' consumer segment might have a larger effect on behavioural attitude while targeting 'Familiarity sensitive', and 'Unfamiliarity' consumer segments might have a larger effect on behaviour. Additionally, targeting consumers with lower education and income, those following omnivore dietary patterns with a normal BMI may have a larger effect on food waste reduction behavioural change. Given the limited number of studies integrating the ASE framework with food choice motives, and sociodemographic and lifestyle factors, this study provides a framework for the definition of targeted interventions to counter increasing food waste in university canteens in Denmark or similar countries.

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CRediT authorship contribution statement

Sujita Pandey: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Software, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Mausam Budhathoki:** Methodology, Software, Validation, Visualization, Writing – review & editing. **Federico Jose Armando Perez-Cueto:** Conceptualization, Supervision, Validation, Writing – review & editing. **Marianne Thomsen:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Methodology, Project administration, Resources, Supervision, Validation, Visualization, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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